

**LANGUAGE AND GOVERNANCE: A PRAGMATIC STUDY OF ACHEBE'S
*ANTHILLS OF THE SAVANNAH***

ROSECOLETTE N. EWURUM Ph.D ,

Department of Languages and Communication
Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri

08063523211

Colrin68@yahoo.com

I. CHIMA IGBOKWE PH.D

Department of Languages and Humanities
Abia State Polytechnic Aba

08033427161

chimaigbokwe87@yahoo.com

&

ANKOLIE OKORO PH.D

Department of Languages and Communication
Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri

Abstract

This study examines language use in governance and its implication for positive nationhood in Achebe's *Anthills of the Savannah*. In Nigeria and Africa, many leaders use language devoid of politeness considerations and this situation has caused various shades of clashes that hinder positive nationhood. Consequently, the face-threatening acts and violations of politeness maxims in a leader's language use in the text are assessed. The strategies for face-threatening act are highlighted. Forty excerpts selected from the study text serve as data for examining the variables identified. Goffman's (1967) Face-act theory, Leech's (1973) Politeness Maxims and Austin's (1972) Speech Act theories constitute the theoretical approaches for data analysis. From the investigation, it is discovered that utterances of a leader devoid of politeness and face considerations are harbingers of conflict. It is recommended that such matters as language use in administration should not be neglected.